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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

Deliverable 4.2: Development of a generic living lab governance framework

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission
BMC	Business model canvas
DCM	Data communication middleware
DT	Digital Twin
EU	European Union
EUMO	Euromobilita
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensor
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GF	Governance framework
IMGW	Institute of Meteorology and water Economy

IoT	Internet of Things
IV	Infrastrutture Venete
IWT	Inland waterway transport
IWW	Inland waterway
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SB	Smart Buoy
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
UI	User interface
UNEW	University of Newcastle

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Table of Contents

Document summary information	1
Revision history	2
List of abbreviations.....	2
1. Executive Summary.....	5
1.1. Introduction	6
1.2. Mapping CRISTAL project outputs	6
1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	8
2. Development of the scope of the governance framework	9
3. Impact of the digital CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework.....	13
3.1. The Synchromodal Corridor Management System governance framework.....	13
3.2. The Digital Twin governance framework.....	17
4. Impact of the physical CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework.....	20
4.1. The Acoustic Emission Technology governance framework.....	20
4.2. The Fiber Optic Sensor Technology governance framework	22
4.3. The Smart Buoy governance framework	28
4.4. The Subsurface Inspection Radar governance framework	31
5. Validation and implementation of the governance framework	35
5.1. Governance framework elements	35
5.2. Relevant governance framework stakeholders	35
5.3. Implementation of the governance framework	35
5.4. Implementation of the governance framework through the Living Lab	36
6. Conclusion	37
7. References	39
8. List of tables.....	40
9. List of figures.....	40
10. Appendices	41
Annex I – Questionnaire outline	41
Annex II – Validation questions of the governance frameworks.....	43
Annex III – Detailed overview of the CRISTAL developments in relation to the governance framework	44

1. Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.2 presents, discusses and validates governance frameworks (GFs) of the different CRISTAL technologies (both the digital technologies and the physical technologies). First, a general overview of governance frameworks based on existing literature is given. This is followed by the development of a general framework, explaining all necessary elements: the introduction and purpose; the governance principles; the organizational structure, planning and coordination; Information collection, sharing, and operability; performance monitoring and reporting; risk management; regulatory compliance, stakeholder communication and engagement; continuous improvement; and lastly the funding and resource management. After this general introduction, six GFs are created based on both the general GF and the answers from questionnaires provided by all the technology providers. The choice to create six GFs was based on the structure of the technologies created during the CRISTAL project. The Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) is the overarching technology. The Digital Twins (DTs) receives input from the four other technologies and acts as an input for the SCMS. The Acoustic Emission technology (AE), Fiber Optic Sensor technology (FOS), Smart Buoy (SB), and Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) provide raw data that will be visualized in the DTs visualization platforms. The last part of this deliverable validates the GFs internally. Towards that, all technology providers had to review their respective GF and answer a few questions regarding the completeness and correctness of it. As a result, it was confirmed that the GFs can be implemented as all necessary elements are present and applicable but need some further defining and addressing to ensure viability and value creation. This is since details on certain issues (e.g. funding, risk management, etc.) have, in most cases, not been decided upon but should be in the future or after the project duration, when further development takes place. As the project progresses, the governance frameworks can be supplemented and completed, and a complete validation of the governance frameworks will take place during the Living Labs.

1.1. Introduction

The main objectives of this deliverable are:

- Determining the impact of the CRISTAL technologies developments on the governance structure,
- Determining the generic governance framework to support WP2 and WP3 developments work.

This governance framework has as goal, namely, to support stakeholders and decision makers to mitigate disruptions on the inland waterway transport (IWT) network. This entails both the operations of the vessels (corridor management) as well as the (predictive) maintenance of the IWT infrastructure. The following subtasks are foreseen:

- Development of the governance framework, indicating the importance of governance frameworks and discussing the necessary elements (link to task T.4.2.3).
- Determination of the impact of the of the digital CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework, establishing the governance frameworks for the SCMS and DT (link to T4.2.1 & T4.2.3).
- Determination of the impact of the developed CRISTAL technologies on the governance frameworks, by creating governance frameworks of the Acoustic Emission technology, the Fiber Optic Sensors, the Smart buoys and the Subsurface Radar inspection system (link to T4.2.2 & T4.2.3).
- Validation of the established governance frameworks internally by having the project partners reading the created governance framework and providing their opinion regarding the completeness and correctness of it (T4.2.4).

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL project outputs

This deliverable is divided in four main chapters, which are linked to the different subtasks as provided in the GA for T4.2 (which is strictly connected with D4.2). An overview of the contributing partners per section is show below in Table 1.

In Table 2 alignment of D4.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions is showed.

Table 1: Authors and contributing partners

Section	Contributing Partner(s)	Authors by affiliation
Section 2. Development of the scope of the governance framework	Marie Cryns, Edwin van Hassel, Rose Otello, Paola Bottega	UnAnt, SOG, ENEA
Section 3. GF for the Digital CRISTAL technologies	Marie Cryns, Edwin van Hassel, Orestis Tsolakis, Bjorn Kramer	UnAnt, CERTH, FRAUNHOFER
Section 4. GF for the Physical CRISTAL technologies	Marie Cryns, Edwin van Hassel, Emilia O'Neil, Luca Zenneta, Theo Tsenis, Tadeusz Rudnicki, Mark Robinson	UnAnt, UniTra, CERTH, L-PIT, UNEW
Section 5. Validation and implementation of the GF	Marie Cryns, Edwin van Hassel, Rose Otello, Paola Bottega	UnAnt, SOG

Table 2 Alignment of D4.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)
DELIVERABLE		
<i>D4.2 Development of a living labs governance framework</i>	In this report the generic governance framework is developed. This governance framework has as goal to mitigate disruptions on the IWT network. This entails both the operations of the vessels (corridor management) as well as the (predictive) maintenance of the IWT infrastructure (WP2 technologies).	Section 2 - 5
CORRESPONDING TASKS		
T.4.2.1: Determine the impact of the developed technologies (WP2) on the governance model	Determination of the impact of the developed CRISTAL technologies on the governance frameworks, by creating governance frameworks of the Acoustic Emission technology, the Fiber Optic Sensors, the Smart buoys and the Subsurface Radar inspection system	Section 4. Impact of the physical CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework

<p>T.4.2.2: Determine the impact of the corridor management system (WP3) on the governance model.</p>	<p>Determination of the impact of the of the digital CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework establishing the governance frameworks for the SCMS and DT</p>	<p>Section 3. Impact of the digital CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework</p>
<p>T.4.2.3: Develop the generic governance framework</p>	<p>Development of the governance framework, indicating the importance of governance frameworks and discussing the necessary elements</p>	<p>Section 2. Development of the scope of the governance framework</p>
<p>T.4.2.4: Joint Workshop with Advisory Board, pilot partners and Stakeholders to validate governance framework</p>	<p>Validation of the established governance frameworks internally by having the project partners reading the created governance framework and providing their opinion regarding the completeness and correctness of it</p>	<p>Section 5. Validation and implementation of the governance framework</p>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into four main chapters:

- In **chapter 2** the development of the theoretical governance framework is worked out.
- In **chapter 3**, the impact of the Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) on the governance frameworks is determined. Here, the same is done for the Digital Twin (DT), as this technology and its data visualization will be an input for the SCMS.
- **Chapter 4** includes the impact of the developed CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework where the Smart Buoy (SB), Acoustic Emission (AE), Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS), and Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) will be discussed.
- Eventually, the governance frameworks will be internally validated in **chapter 5**.

The deliverable finishes with an overall conclusion where the main findings are presented.

2. Development of the scope of the governance framework

A governance framework is “a guidance system composed of standard management practices designed to suit the organization.” (Talbot & Jakeman, 2011). A governance framework refers to the structure, policies, processes, and standards that an organization or an ecosystem uses to guide decision-making, ensure accountability, and achieve its objectives. Therefore, policies, processes, structures, and procedures need to be determined and acknowledged to create a framework which will help the organization, its objectives and its stakeholders. The senior management and operational level of a company or organization use governance frameworks to obtain a clear understanding of all expectations, objectives, performances, reporting requirements and risks. Therefore, governance frameworks shape and set cultures, objectives, risks, values etc. (Smith and Brooks, 2013). As established in D4.1, all stakeholders in the organizational environment must be integrated in the framework to be able to achieve the best results (Loshin, 2009). Therefore, a holistic governance framework must consist of certain components. Table 3 lists the components of the governance framework, together with the description of each component. In addition, Figure 1 visualizes these components in one figure of framework.

Table 3: Components of a governance framework

Components	Description
Introduction and purpose	What is the framework for and what is its purpose?
Governance principles	Key governance principles need to be identified to guide decision-making and collaboration.
Organizational structure	What is the organizational structure, what are the key stakeholders, and what are their roles and responsibilities?
Planning and coordination	Processes for planning should be established, mechanisms for coordination among stakeholders should be defined and procedures for conflict resolution and decision making in case of disagreements should be developed.
Information collection, sharing, and operability	Protocols and standards for data sharing and interoperability need to be established. The type of information that has to be shared has to be defined and the data privacy and security considerations must be addressed.
Performance monitoring and reporting	Performance indicators and mechanisms for monitoring and reporting on KPIs need to be developed, and responsibilities for data collection, analysis, and reporting need to be defined.

Risk management	Potential risks and vulnerabilities need to be identified, a risk management framework needs to be developed, and processes for monitoring and addressing risks need to be established.
Regulatory compliance	Relevant regulations, laws, and standards need to be identified, procedures and controls to ensure compliance with the regulatory requirements need to be developed, and mechanisms for reporting and addressing non-compliance issues need to be established.
Stakeholder engagement and communication	Strategies for engaging and collaborating with stakeholders need to be developed, communication channels for sharing information, updates, and best practices need to be established, and a culture of transparency and inclusivity to encourage stakeholder participation needs to be fostered.
Continuous improvement	Processes for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the system need to be implemented, feedback from stakeholders need to be encouraged, periodic reviews need to be conducted, and a culture of innovation and learning needs to be fostered.
Funding and resource management	Funding resources to support operations and the development of the system need to be identified and secured, mechanisms for resource allocation, budgeting, and financial reporting need to be developed, and processes for monitoring and optimizing resource utilization need to be established.

Figure 1: Visualization of the general (theoretical) governance framework

This generic concept of the governance model is going to be applied to inland waterway eco system. In these eco systems new technologies are going to be developed to improve the resilience of the inland

waterway ecosystem. The CRISTAL project is focused on Europe with three different pilot areas (Poland, Italy and France). All of these pilot areas have a different governance structure that will be developed further in D.4.4 and in WPs 6 till 9 (WPs dealing with the pilots in the project). The main generic overview of the main regulatory bodies in Europe are shown below:

1. The European union (EU):

- The European Union plays a crucial role in coordinating and harmonizing policies related to inland waterway transport. Key legislative frameworks include the European Directive 2006/87/EC on the harmonization of the laws of the member states relating to inland waterway transport. This directive establishes common rules for the promotion of inland waterway transport, covering safety, crew qualifications, and technical standards for vessels.

2. Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine (CCNR):

- The CCNR is an international organization that focuses on the regulation and coordination of navigation on the Rhine River. While it is not an EU institution, it collaborates closely with the EU to ensure harmonization of regulations and standards. The CCNR develops technical regulations and agreements among the participating countries to facilitate seamless navigation on the Rhine.

3. National and regional authorities:

- Each EU member state has its own national (and regional) authorities responsible for the regulation and management of inland waterways within its borders. These authorities work in coordination with EU directives and regulations to ensure a consistent approach to inland waterway governance.

The detailed developed of the governance framework for the three different pilot areas will be developed in D.4.4. Next to the differences in the regulatory structure of the 3 pilots, also the 3 pilots have different technologies that will be implemented/tested. Therefore this deliverable will discuss a governance framework for the **Synchromodal Corridor Management System**, the **Digital Twins**, and the **four technologies** of the CRISTAL project.

Figure 2 shows all technologies and their application in each case. A distinction between the different technologies was made based on the material state of the technology itself. First, there are digital innovations, and second, there are developed physical sub-models which theoretically could be offered as a standalone application, but in practice will be (in)directly connected with the SCMS. This is because the technologies generate raw data which needs to be processed and visualized to generate meaningful information and knowledge. Also, not all technologies will be fully implemented and tested in real time during the project, but they will be developed in a laboratory (indicated with O in figure 2, all the real-life tested applications are indicated with X). But their functionality could become part of the SCMS and therefore it is included in the scope of the governance framework.

		Innovation	Can be offered as a stand-alone application (own BM)	Can only be offered as part of the SCMS	France	Poland	Italy
Digital innovations	a	Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Yes		○	○	○
	b	Digital twins	Yes (to infra manager)	Can feed data into the SCMS	○	○	○
Developed PHYSICAL submodels	1	Intelligent/Smart Buoy System (I/SBS)	Yes	Feeds into Dtwinn & SCMS		X	
	2	Acoustic Emission (AE) Technology	Yes	Feeds into Dtwinn & SCMS	X		X
	3	Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS) Technology	Yes	Feeds into Dtwinn & SCMS			○
	4	Structural health monitoring (SHM) of engineered infrastructures inspection radar technology/ Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) Technology	Yes	Can also be linked to Dtwinn & SCMS	X		

Figure 2: Technologies and innovations created, implemented, and tested in the CRISTAL project

3. Impact of the digital CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework

In this chapter, governance frameworks of the SCMS and DTs will be discussed. The SCMS strives to enhance transport operations through real-time information, dynamic planning, and optimal resource utilization, while supporting decision making. Within the CRISTAL project, the SCMS is designed from the point of view of inland navigation, where new CRISTAL technologies are used as data inputs. These new technologies are the Digital Twins, Fiber Optic Sensors, the Smart Buoy System, Acoustic Emission technology, and the Subsurface Inspection Radar. Data from the AE, FOS, SB and SIR will be gathered via a Data Broker. From this, data is then forwarded to the Data communication middleware (DCM) of the SCMS. The pilot countries for the SCMS are Italy, Poland and France (CERTH, 2023).

During the project, three different Digital Twins (DT) will be created. A DT is a digital representation of real-world equipment, devices or systems (Augustine, 2020). The DTs created as part of CRISTAL project, include user interfaces (UI) and data conversion engines where data from the data broker are processed to generate information and knowledge useful to inform the SCMS. Three different DTs are created, where each DT displays a different type data from the data broker. Subsequently, the DTs can be used both as a stand-alone technology and as an input to the SCMS, making the SCMS a consumer of the DT's output. The main uses of the DT technology include predictive maintenance and navigability forecasting (e.g. for the latter DT will forecast the water heights in the Italian Po River through historical data and data received from sensors) (Fraunhofer IML, 2023).

3.1. The Synchromodal Corridor Management System governance framework

3.1.1 Governance principles

To describe what the SCMS entails, nine characteristics/requirements are defined by the WP3 project partners and can be understood as governance principles. First of all, the SCMS will facilitate the switching between transportation modes through proposals for the optimal utilization of multimodal transport network resources. Next, the SCMS is a cooperation between transport actors and real-time optimization and network service design. It provides tactical and operational decisions support influenced by planning horizon and dynamic transportation planning, while taking multicommodity and multi-stakeholder characteristics in consideration. Lastly, the SCMS provides real time network information, transparency, and data exchange (CERTH, 2023). These characteristics can also be seen as the governance principles indicated by the governance framework components in Table 3. Components such as actors who own/host the SCMS, the revenue scheme, costs and profits have not been included in this version of the government framework, as the SCMS is at a stage of development in which only estimations can be made. These estimations can be consulted in Deliverable 4.3 regarding the Business Models of the technologies.

3.1.2 Organizational structure

To create a governance framework, the organizational structure of the SCMS should be identified. Therefore, key stakeholders should be identified, and their different roles and responsibilities. As the SCMS will be implemented and tested to a certain extent in the three pilot cases (some components will depend on the availability of data in each pilot), all stakeholders for the SCMS should be identified. For this step, the stakeholder frameworks created in D4.1 can be used. These stakeholder frameworks show the key stakeholders of each CRISTAL pilot case (French, Italian, and Polish pilot case). According to the WP3 project partners who are responsible for the creation of the SCMS, the most important actors/stakeholders which can benefit from the SCMS are:

- Shippers
- Logistics service providers or the 3/4/5PL companies
- Transport companies
- Deepsea and inland ports
- Barge operators
- Public administration and regulators of IWT
- Calamity Abatement Operators

As the SCMS supports the logistics operational aspect of the inland waterway (IWW), the actors mentioned above have different roles and responsibilities such as providing transport and logistics services, planning and scheduling shipments, high level (administration level) decision making regarding infrastructure development and drafting of regulations and guidelines development. Additionally, two stakeholders contributing to the development and operation of the SCMS should be included. These are the developer and operator of the system (CERTH) and the technological providers that will provide the input for the system, such as Fraunhofer for the DT, the sensor owners or the owners of other external platforms that will be connected for providing data and services to the SCMS.

3.1.3 Planning and coordination

It is necessary to consider factors such as infrastructure capacity and modal connections when establishing a process for the planning of the SCMS. When looking at the process planning of the SCMS, it refers to the operational process of the SCMS platform. Therefore, CERTH designs and develops a platform which includes the foreseen process for collecting and pushing the information with the relevant stakeholders, the assessment of information for predicted disruption by the DT, the evaluation and suggestion of alternative options, etc. Information is pushed because of the presence of a push notification mechanism. The “Early detection & info” component can push the alerting information upon request and preferences of the registered user. The SCMS will support the decision making for the planning of logistics operations, which is why the actual planning decisions will remain in the hands of the relevant stakeholders as it is today. Coordination mechanisms need to identify the activities provided to coordinate the actors/stakeholders of the SCMS. These mechanisms have not been defined yet, although the SCMS will not foresee to foster direct contact through the platform itself. All relevant and paying actors/stakeholders will have access to the provided information on the SCMS platform based on their roles and credentials, as some information can be sensitive (e.g. the route assessment requests that a specific logistics service provider has asked the system to provide). The communication channels between them will remain as they are today. Therefore, there is no need for a specialized conflict addressing mechanism if conflicts occur

between the actors/stakeholders as the SCMS is a monitoring and decision supporting tool and can therefore provide information by its functionalities which can help actors resolve their own disagreements.

3.1.4 Information collection, sharing, and interoperability

The SCMS has a data processing and information hub which is a “comprehensive platform that gathers external data and provides stakeholders with valuable insights and real-time information to support decisions regarding the synchromodal transport network.” (CERTH, 2023). This hub includes two components: a data exchange tool and a data processing and information tool. The first tool is designed to enhance the cooperation between stakeholders and ensure effective data sharing. If the SCMS will be further developed after the CRISTAL project duration, stakeholders will be able to share data and information on transport services, capacity, etc. to reduce the risk of misunderstandings and increase transparency. The data processing and information tools offer a comprehensive set of tools and data to support informed decision-making about the synchromodal transport network to stakeholders (CERTH, 2023). The data and information that will be shared through the SCMS originates from sensors (e.g., Acoustic Emission technology), the Digital Twins, and CRISTAL pilot partners, while other data and information originates either from open sources (e.g., rail schedules, and most notably EURIS) or other stakeholders/external systems through direct contact. Therefore, specific protocols and standards will be defined based on the work of CERTH, L-PIT and Fraunhofer regarding the data exchange and sharing. Additionally, each actor/stakeholder of the SCMS will receive access to the data according to their role and credentials. This is to protect the data that may be sensitive and to create trust among all actors/stakeholders. The SCMS will be able to be interoperable by considering also other existing systems when thinking about standards and protocols for the data exchange.

3.1.5 Performance monitoring and reporting

The final KPIs that will prove the usefulness of the SCMS have not been decided yet. However, several have been considered but need to be further assessed. Some examples include the reduction of the lead time due to the SCMS use in case of disruptions (in comparison to the required time to resume operations today in case of a disruption), the CO₂ emissions and/or total costs savings, the percentage increase of the rail share compared to road in the cases of disruptions, etc. The performance indicators will be calculated through the use cases that will be tested in the pilots of the project. The monitoring and reporting of the KPIs will be part of the observatory functionality of the SCMS. Detailed performance indicators regarding the measurement of efficiency and effectiveness of the SCMS have also yet to be decided.

3.1.6 Risk management

Risks and vulnerabilities identification and mitigation of the SCMS are not included in WP3 activities but can be included in the business model for the SCMS, which will be created later in the project. Overall, there is a project risk management plan that will be drafted in the context of Task 12.5. Mainly the SCMS developers (CERTH) and the project coordination are involved in and responsible for the risk management of the SCMS.

3.1.7 Regulatory compliance

The actors responsible for the regulatory side of the governance framework have also been identified in D4.1. Here, there are different regulatory levels for each pilot case and therefore, the procedures, mechanisms and controls will differ in each case. This means that the federal and local administration which are related to the IWT developments in each country are of importance, together with the EU regulators related to IWT. In D3.1, some information was provided regarding laws and regulations which are relevant for and apply to the SCMS: “To maintain its efficacy and efficiency in controlling the transportation of commodities over inland waterways inside the EU, a synchromodal corridor management system must adhere to European Union (EU) legislation and standards. The system must, first and foremost, adhere to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU, which establishes guidelines for the protection of natural people regarding the processing of personal data. This implies that the system must guarantee the security and privacy of any personal data processed as well as the right of individuals to access and modify their personal data. Additionally, the system must abide by all EU-issued environmental protection rules and directives, including those that address waste management, the prevention of air and water pollution, and the conservation of species and ecosystems. This calls on the system to think about how its operations could influence the environment and to take action to lessen any negative effects. Moreover, Inland Waterway Navigation (IWN) Directive, which establishes uniform guidelines for the safe and effective operation of inland waterway transport in the EU, is one such legislation that the system must also abide with. This covers legislation governing inland waterways infrastructure development and operation as well as laws governing safety, security, and environmental preservation.” (CERTH, 2023). In addition, some standards are also applicable to the SCMS, with the most notable ones emerging from the River Information Services (RIS). “RIS is the concept whereby information services in inland navigation support traffic and transport management in inland navigation, including interfaces with other modes of transport. Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonized river information services on the EU’s inland waterways (RIS Directive) requires Member States to implement RIS according to certain standards.” (CESNI). Overall, the compliance with regulatory requirements is checked during the development of the SCMS components and functionalities by the developers (e.g., when concluding on the required data for a functionality, the developers consider whether some of this data is subject to the GDPR). However, a more comprehensive review of the laws, regulations and standards is needed and foreseen to be created in the next stage of the project.

3.1.8 Stakeholder engagement and communication

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration can take place in different ways such as regular meetings, workshops or feedback mechanisms. In case of the SCMS, this has yet to be decided, though the system will certainly need stakeholder feedback. The time plan and method of the stakeholder engagement have not been defined yet. Additionally, no communication channels for stakeholders will be created within the SCMS platform, as of right now, but it can be considered in the future. However, no direct communication will be possible via the SCMS platform, as stated in chapter 3.1.3. Planning and coordination of the SCMS.

3.1.9 Continuous improvement

For continuous improvements, periodic reviews need to be established to identify gaps and possible useful extensions emerging from the operational experience of the system (SCMS). The implementation of periodic reviews in case of the SCMS still have to be decided. After the development of the system, it has

to be decided if the estimated needs for future improvements justify the establishment of periodic reviews. If periodic reviews take place, actors/stakeholders will be included and will have a role in providing feedback on the system operation. Any proposed change or extension for the SCMS included in the periodic review will be evaluated regarding its feasibility and depending on the outcome it may be implemented through a system update.

3.1.10 Funding and resource management

This has yet to be decided: the business model of the SCMS has not been created yet, and the supplier of the system and the price of it have yet to be defined. Further information regarding this part of the governance framework can be found in Deliverable 4.3. (Business model and cost-benefit analysis).

3.2. The Digital Twin governance framework

The DTs are a part of the SCMS that will host and calculate the data collected from the physical technologies and innovations. In addition, the DTs can also operate on their own. During the project, three DTs will be created: a DT focusing on the locks and AE, a DT focusing on the rivers and SBs, and a DT focusing on the water levels. These will be a theoretical application in all three pilot cases. For the French pilot case, the digital twin is designed for the lock and buoy use case. The Italian case, specifically the part of the Po managed by AiPo, will use the DT for shallow water forecasts, to ensure trouble-free traffic operations, and the support of dredging operations, while the part of the Po managed by Infrastrutture Venete (IV) will use the digital twin for real-time management of alarms, historical data management, controlled data access management, create the possibility for remote interventions, ease the use by the operator, and checking the reliability of the acquired data. The functionality of the DT in case of Poland is unknown (ENEA, 2022; Fiedler et al., 2022). This questionnaire was filled out by the WP5 project partners from Fraunhofer.

3.2.1 Governance principles

When asked about the key (governance) principles that will guide the management of the DTs, security and interoperability were appointed as the most important ones. On the one hand, the DTs should be secure in their use. On the other hand, the DTs must be able to communicate with other systems and sensor technologies. Additionally, the DTs should be able to exchange data in both directions, regardless of the form and size of their respective different functions.

3.2.2 Organizational structure

When the organizational structure is discussed, infrastructure managers, transport operators (via the SCMS), and information suppliers (for the SCMS) are the most important actors and stakeholders. These also have different roles and responsibilities, divided per DT. In case of the DT linked to the locks, data quality and management are the most important for the users. The admin of this DT has as main focus on the security of the data. For the second DT (focusing on the rivers and SBs), the users must be able to use the DT and see which data is visualized. The admin of this DT has as main role the security of the DT. The DT focusing on the water levels has the same roles for users and admin as the river and SB DT.

3.2.3 Planning and coordination

For all DTs, process planning will be done as it is required based on D5.1 in coordination with all pilots, the SCMS and the technology providers. However, an external coordination mechanism among actors and stakeholders does not exist now. A coordination mechanism does exist internally for Fraunhofer, and the CRISTAL project partners via work-packages and individual meetings. Therefore, no mechanism in case of conflicts or disagreements between external actors and stakeholders is provided.

3.2.4 Information collection, sharing, and interoperability

Data sharing is one of the main tasks of the DTs. Each DT has two directions of data flows: an inbound and an outbound direction. The inbound flow divides the data into two groups: a push group and a pull group. The push group can be sensors or other platforms for example that sent information to the DT in case of a new event happening. This includes the Acoustic Emission system and the Radar Inspection system. In the pull group, data is actively collected by the DT from various sources such as sensors or other platforms. The outbound data flow goes to the frontend of the DT or to the SCMS via an alert system. Overall, not all data generated by the DTs will be shared. Only results and processed data will be available. In addition, the data which is shared is also based on the role of each actor/stakeholder, e.g., the infrastructure manager will only see their own lock on their interface. The individual access rights are decided and distributed by each project pilot. Subsequently, this has also led to the need for a security log-in into the system. The collection and sharing of the data have to be very secure, therefore secured communication is needed and is made possible by using e.g., OAuth-Security and Keycloak-Server for Web-Security. For the exchange of data, JSON-Format is used, if possible. OpenApi specification with Swagger UI is used for the interfaces of the different DTs. However, due to the many different data formats and sizes, standardization does not make sense here. Next, the DTs are not responsible for the data quality. The DT only processes the provided data, e.g., if the data of the buoy is inconsistent, then the DT will show less valid results. However, a data cleaning process is integrated to assure consistent data. Lastly, it is important to mention the interoperability of the DTs. All DTs will be interoperable with other products and systems by using loose coupling for the frontend. It is possible to switch it and develop or use your own product or system. Using REST-Interfaces for the communication creates the possibility to retrieve all information or some parts for other systems. So, it could be possible to send information to the AIPO-Dashboard and integrate it. It is also possible to receive or send data to the DTs. There will be an alert/notification system which pushes information to other system like the SCMS, when a certain threshold will be reached. Using JSON-Format and the OpenApi specification with Swagger UI the interfaces are very open (but secured). However, insofar as these requirements are to be met, an administrative and programmatic effort is necessary each time. This ensures the security of the application.

3.2.5 Performance monitoring and reporting

As with the SCMS, KPIs have not been defined yet and the monitoring and reporting of them have to be discussed further.

3.2.6 Risk management

As mentioned a few times before, IT security is very important and the right security standards (e.g., a single-sign-on) are considered and incorporated during the developments of the DTs. However, risk

management during the creation of the prototypes of the DTs is not provided, but the creators do care about the overall security. The project pilots, technology providers and Fraunhofer IML will further discuss the risk management of the DTs.

3.2.7 Regulatory compliance

As every technology, the DTs are compliant to EU laws and GDPR for data sharing, and protection regulations such as EU Regulation 2018/1725 and the Data Governance Act (DGA). The compliance with the laws, standards and regulations will not be checked as of right now, maybe in the future.

3.2.8 Stakeholder engagement and communication

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration will internally take place through meetings. Externally, no major involvement of additional stakeholders apart from the consortium will happen because the DTs will only reach prototype status within the CRISTAL project. Communication channels for the internal actors and stakeholders are provided (e.g., Teams, deliverables, conferences, etc.).

3.2.9 Continuous improvement

Feedback from the project pilots and periodic reviews will be considered during the current development of the DTs, and this will happen on a regular basis.

3.2.10 Funding and resource management

The last part of the governance framework is the most difficult one. Therefore, we refer to Deliverable 4.3 where business models of all technologies are created and where a cost and benefit analysis has been made for the DTs.

4. Impact of the physical CRISTAL technologies on the governance framework

In this part of the Deliverable, governance frameworks for the four technologies of the CRISTAL project are created. The four technologies discussed in this part are:

- the Acoustic Emission technology (4.1),
- the Fiber Optic sensors (4.2),
- the Smart Buoys (4.3),
- and the Subsurface Inspection Radars (4.4).

Again, the governance frameworks were created based on questionnaires sent out to the project partners in charge of the development of the technologies. The technology has been installed in two locks (Conca Di Baricetta and Isola Serafini) by the CERTH team and measurements are being taken to eventually feed the Data Broker and Digital Twin.

4.1. The Acoustic Emission Technology governance framework

The Acoustic Emission System (AE) facilitates the assessment of the status of the lock gates as well as preventive and predictive maintenance of water lock gates. The system is a Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) tool meaning it periodically reads the monitored structure to measure the working status. The AE system currently gathers data of the gates' normal operation and the aging effect of it. This data will train the model to provide identification when the structure is out of the good area of operation. At this moment, the technology has reached maturity and is a commercial stage of development. The AE is mainly useful to relevant maintenance managers, calamity abatement operators, and barge operators for efficient maintenance planning and risk mitigation. The designated pilot sites for this technology are in France and Italy (ENEA, 2023).

4.1.1 Governance principles

According to CERTH, the developers of the Acoustic Emission Technology, the main governance principles are ensuring the correct mounting of the sensors and providing good telecommunication. The AE sensors need to be firmly mounted on the body that must be inspected to be able to work properly. Consequently, the proper installation of the sensors ensures the communication with the data broker of the Digital Twin (DT), where the received data is displayed for end-users to consult. As a result, the management of the installation and communication with the data broker are key governance principles.

4.1.2 Organizational structure

The organizational structure is mostly dictated by the DT operator. The DT operator observes the communication between the DT and the AE, and if it is working right. If the communication does not work properly, the pilot technician will be alerted, and this actor will check if the system has power and can communicate. To avoid problems, the pilot technician will need to perform periodic maintenance on sensor mounting.

The key stakeholders of the AE system are:

- DT operator
- pilot technician
- maintenance managers (for port-based infrastructures)
- calamity abatement operators
- barge operators

These actors use the AE technology as for efficient preventive and predictive maintenance planning and risk mitigation.

4.1.3 Planning and coordination

As the AE technology is still in the early stages of maturing, no process planning has been provided yet, no coordination mechanisms are in place and no mechanisms of conflicts are available. When looking at the future, those three mechanisms will not be offered according to the AE developers.

4.1.4 Information collection, sharing, and interoperability

Data collected via the AE will be shared with the data broker which is under development by Fraunhofer. After the data is collected by the AE, it will be sent to said data broker interface where a specific format is being used to visualize the data. All collected data is for internal use, while only the results will be displayed by the DT. This is also the only other system the AE will interact with. Eventually, the data will provide a percentage of water lock gate failure, which will be visualized in the DT interface. Data quality is ensured by automatic testing of the sensor data and periodic maintenance. In addition, the right application of the sensors on the right infrastructural bodies is necessary.

4.1.5 Performance monitoring and reporting

There is one main key performance indicator, and that is the good acoustic conductance of the sensors on the inspected body. This indicator will be monitored via the AE itself, as it has an internal auto-testing feature which must be executed periodically by the pilot's technician. The main actors or stakeholders involved in the risk management are the DT manager or operator, and the pilot's technician.

4.1.6 Risk management

As AE is a mature technology, meaning it is currently operating, and all relevant risks and vulnerabilities have been identified and addressed. There are three kinds of risks:

- Sensors are not correctly or properly installed
- Sensors get detached from the inspection body
- Connection with the data broker gets lost or the AE system is even broken.

The first risk can be identified by auto-testing signals to the sensors. The second one can be identified by observing from the DT console that no data is collected and displayed. The last risk can be identified by a simple inspection where the DT does not receive data and the user does not see a visualization of the data.

4.1.7 Regulatory compliance

In terms of regulatory compliance, it was indicated to not be applicable for the AE. Overall, based on the other questionnaires, the same rules, laws and standards regarding data sharing and collection applies such as the GDPR regulations.

4.1.8 Stakeholder engagement and communication

As for this moment, stakeholder engagement and collaboration possibilities are still under process and will be implemented if it is requested.

4.1.9 Continuous improvement

Periodic reviews will be conducted by the pilot's technician. Nothing has been decided on further reviews or feedback moments.

4.1.10 Funding and resource management

The last part of the governance framework is the most difficult one. Therefore, we refer to Deliverable 4.3 where business models of all technologies are created and where a cost and benefit analysis has been made.

4.2. The Fiber Optic Sensor Technology governance framework

The FOS Technology is a technology developed estimate the height of the sand-dune on the river bed in the critical points of the riverbed in which the technology is installed. This provides the opportunity to monitor the navigability of free-flowing waterways. These sensors utilize weight sensors, strategically placed at critical section lines, to identify sediments pileups. This timely detection enables more efficient dredging planning, minimizing productivity losses caused by these obstructions. The end users of FOS are: infrastructure manager (direct users: they will receive from the sensor the estimation) and then barge operators, logistic service providers and calamity abatements operators (indirect users: they will receive information about the navigability based on the sensor estimation). The sensors will also indirectly generate data that will be contributing to the digital twins and the SCMS (ENEA, 2022; Fiedler et al., 2022). This technology is meant to be implemented in the pilot sites in Italy and Poland having free flowing water ways; however, during the CRISTAL project, the technology development will only reach the system prototype demonstration in operational environment (TRL7) not in the river sites.

4.2.1 Governance principles

The governance principles of the FOS technology are linked to the FOS specifications and Internet of Things (IoT) solution architecture. The FOS specifications are based on the data collection requirements and the IoT solution architecture (i.e. CRISTAL system architecture). ENEA will lease with other parties involved in the CRISTAL project to produce smart CRISTAL services, as can be seen in Figure 3. According to its internal rules in providing commercial services and producing commercial products, ENEA will outsource part of the activity. In the framework of the project, a (Small Medium Enterprise) is envisaged for that task, namely ASCANIO srl which is a ENEA Spinoff.

Figure 3: IoT governance roles and responsibilities, source: ENEA

In general, the IoT governance framework for the FOS technology should include:

- **Interoperability in the technology dimension:** this interoperability should take place across the different layers of the IoT reference architecture. This can be very specific based on the end-user's need and needs to be aligned with the communication standards and protocols of other digital ecosystems in the organization. In addition, a clear data lifecycle management for all datasets needs to be generated by the IoT ecosystem, given its specificity and frequency.
- **Rules in the operations dimension:** rules regarding integrated digital service management, workflow integration management, and a well-defined service catalogue with other IT systems should be in place. Real-time insights and data analytics are the most important aspects of this dimension. The specificity and frequency of FOS data implies a high level of correlation control points, time-related rules to account for data loss, and data-trust checkpoints for data sources.
- **A well-defined automation scheme** of all relevant resources in the IoT ecosystem.

The FOS devices are included in the physical layer of the CRISTAL platforms. They communicate with their edge routers using specific communication protocols. FOS sensors can transmit data about. In the framework of the project, which only consider a FOS prototype, outsource for the FOS production is envisaged to a SME. The SME that is envisaged to produce the FOS sensors will be responsible for:

- Choosing the right FOS sensor communication devices for the specifically envisaged IoT solution.
- Works with the IoT architect and infrastructure architect to set up communication networks that connect the FOS sensor to the envisaged IoT architecture.
- Finalizing device management policies and principles, including device/product physical security and cybersecurity.

FOS devices have three basic components:

1. One/multiple sensorized plate(s) submerged in the river
2. A fiber optic backbone which delivers the optical signal from the sensorized plate(s)

The FOS interrogator decodes the operational signal in produced digital raw or processed data. This is further transferred in the CRISTAL platform by using any convenient protocol. Eventually, the submerged

installation prevents adopting sensorized plates with on-board stand-alone IoT-architecture (or another more convenient architecture). The IoT architecture is implemented at the FOS interrogator component.

4.2.2 Organizational structure

As for right now, the most important stakeholder regarding the FOS technology is the Infrastructure Manager, that in the framework of the project is AiPo. AiPo realizes and maintains the infrastructures to ensure the free-flow navigation along the Po River from Piacenza to the Adriatic Sea. Their most important roles and responsibilities, referring to the prototype installation done in the framework of the project, are operational maintenance of the FOS technology and the management of it. In addition, the envisaged SME will be responsible under the outsource commitment of ENEA, for the production and lease of the sensors are also key actors, as mentioned above.

4.2.3 Planning and coordination

Process planning for the FOS technology will follow a typical Life Cycle process, conducted by ENEA on the prototype produced in the framework of the project, eventually with fast-ageing activities to get significant response concerning endurance/repair. The process planning includes the following stages:

- Production
- Construction
- Use (incl. maintenance, repair, replacement, refurbishment, and operational energy management)
- End-of-life care

No coordination mechanism or mechanism in case of conflicts/disagreements will be in place for this innovation, as it is not applicable for these sensors.

4.2.4 Information collection, sharing, and interoperability

The FOS technology is part of the physical layer, which is the bottom layer of the CRISTAL system architecture that will guarantee the provision of the CRISTAL services for enhancing navigability in ordinary and extreme weather conditions. The FOS sensors communicate at this layer with their edge routers using specific communication protocols. The sensors will transmit data about strains which are afterwards turned into estimated volumes of sand dunes.

The network layer of the FOS devices transmits data to their respective platforms using the most convenient applicable data wired/wireless networks available (e.g. LoRA). After the data has passed from the FOS sensors through the network layer, it can be aggregated in the middle layer to be visualized on a data visualization platform, which is in the case of the CRISTAL project, the Digital Twin smart monitor for navigability. Next, the aggregated data is processed at the application layer. This gives insights about the environments in which the sensors are embedded in. The shared data will be visible for all ENEA and eventually other actors interested in raw or processed FOS data, and stakeholders to be seen and used. The FOS technology and its generated data will be operable with the CRISTAL Digital Twin, as mentioned before, the CRISTAL SMP and possibly EuRIS.

FOS devices produce and transmit the measured parameters as digital data and can thus be configured to adhere to the most pertinent standard as adopted for data management. No specific restrictions or requirements apply. Since 2010, the International Electrotechnical Commission, IEC, Subcommittee 86C1 has been developing international standards for fiber optic sensors. Operators of critical infrastructure and equipment manufacturers use these standards as guidelines for specifying the measurement performance and reliability of sensor products in a uniform, recognized way. They also help users to select, install and operate DAS systems based on harmonized procedures. Furthermore, the standards create confidence in the technology and its reliability and provide a support mechanism for DAS to be used in new safety-relevant fields. Additionally, they help reduce expenditure by avoiding costly single system validations. To accommodate the complexity of the technology and the wide variety of applications, a matrix structured series of standards was created. IEC 61757, fiber optic sensors - Generic specifications, builds the common base for this series. Three standards specifically address distributed fiber optic sensing as reported below. The one of interest for FOS sensors that will be produced as part of CRISTAL is IEC 61757-1-2, fiber optic sensors – Part 1-2: Strain measurement.

- IEC 61757-3-2, fiber optic sensors – Part 3-2: Acoustic sensing and vibration measurement – Distributed sensing, specifies the terminology, characteristic performance parameters, related test and calculation methods, as well as specific test equipment for interrogation units used in distributed fiber optic acoustic sensing and vibration measurement systems (DAS).
- IEC 61757-2-2, fiber optic sensors – Part 2-2: Temperature measurement – Distributed sensing, defines detailed specifications for distributed temperature measurement, also known as fiber optic distributed temperature sensing (DTS).
- IEC 61757-1-2, fiber optic sensors – Part 1-2: Strain measurement – Distributed sensing based on Brillouin scattering, is close to final voting. The document defines detailed specifications for distributed strain measurements, also known as fiber optic distributed strain sensing (DSS). It is applicable to distributed strain sensing systems based on spontaneous or stimulated Brillouin scattering in the optical fiber sensor, that is, to sensors capable of measuring absolute strain.

In addition to the regulations mentioned above, data quality of the shared FOS data has to be ensured. This depends on the data quality of all involved parts visible in Figure 4.

Figure 4: IoT data quality conceptual framework

When solely focusing on the quality of the data from the FOS sensors, missing value or incorrect value are two possible risk factors. Both risks are further discussed in 4.2.6 Risk management.

Next, standards such as ISO/IEC 25000 regarding a general data quality model, data quality characteristics and structured data, and the ISO 8000 standard regarding characteristics related to information and data quality. This last standard suggests a framework for enhancing the quality of specific types of data methods for managing, measuring, and refining information and data quality.

4.2.5 Performance monitoring and reporting

To monitor the performance of the FOS sensors, the instrumented plate provides a structured spectroscopic optical signal which is analysed and decoded by the FOS Interrogator. The correct condition of the FOS sensor itself can be checked by the analysis of the spectroscopic signature of its signal. The eventual detachment (or early progressive detachment) of the FOS sensor from the transducer element to which it shall stay stuck un structural contact produces, turns in anomalous either drifts or spikes that can be easily detected. To check for possible damage of the FOS backbone, standard techniques for fiber optic communication cables, and standard maintenance/repair procedures can be adopted. The design of the sensorized plate, based on a bending plate schematic design, does not consider moving parts or consumable components easy to go to failure. An inspection program will be considered, possibly in concomitance with the execution of dragging or other general operations on the riverbank. All used procedures and programmes will comply with the ones adopted in CRISTAL for the other physical components and data management.

4.2.6 Risk management

There are five possible factors affecting the FOS technology and its data:

- Sensors
- Environment
- Security
- Privacy
- Network

In addition, some issues or vulnerabilities are:

- Battery problems
- Precision limitation
- Mechanical failures due to dragging operations or other factors
- Device upgrades
- Unstable network
- Non-encrypted

To avoid these risks, issues and vulnerabilities, risk management will be provided and is managed by the producers, and the end-users. These actors will receive training and educational resources.

4.2.7 Regulatory compliance

The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) is the main regulatory actors that has to be accounted for, as mentioned above in 4.2.2. The most relevant law for the FOS technology is the IEC 61757-1-2, Fibre Optic Sensors – Part 1-2: Stain measurement law. The most important standard is the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) standard for Fiber Optic Sensors – Fiber Bragg Grating Interrogator Standard, approved in February of 2021. Next, multiple regulations are to be followed. As far as Interoperability is concerned: the Interoperable Europe Act² and the (Italian) National Digital Data Platform³ Determination (“Piattaforma Digitale Nazionale Dati”) Determination no. 627/2021 of 15 December 2021 - Adoption of the "Guidelines on the technological infrastructure of the National Digital Data Platform for the interoperability of information systems and databases" pursuant to article 50-ter, paragraph 2 of the Legislative Decree 7 March 2005, n. 82 and subsequent amendments should be followed. With respect to data protection, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) should be kept in mind. Lastly, regarding the Life Cycle Assessment, two regulations should be considered. The ISO 14040 general introduction to life cycle assessment concepts and procedures; ISO 14044:2006 requirements and guidelines for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review. Also, the BS EN 15978: 2011 and EDP Environmental Product Declaration is important to keep in mind.

Compliance with policies and procedures and regulatory requirements will be documented and reported in a document with reference to both the production and operational use of FOS. An Environmental Product Declaration, or EPD, i.e. a document which transparently communicates the environmental performance or impact of any product or material over its lifetime is envisaged to be produced for FOS sensors when they will be in production.

4.2.8 Stakeholder engagement and communication

During the creation of the technology, regular project meetings are held between WP2, WP5 and WP7. Communication with other stakeholders is also possible through meetings. Eventually, communication channels will be provided for actors/stakeholders to be able to share their information, insights findings, and lessons learned from the FOS.

4.2.9 Continuous improvement

As the FOS technology will not reach the stage of real installation in the Po River, the periodic reviews and stakeholder feedback are only in place during the CRISTAL project time. This also relates to periodic reviews and feedback.

4.2.10 Funding and resource management

In Deliverable 4.3 an extensive overview of the costs, benefits and business model created for the FOS technology is provided. The FOS business model will be a data-driven model based on data generated by FOS sensors. FOS sensors provide value to customers through the data that will be collected in real time and that can be sold to a third party as a service to inform and support navigability. The supplier of the system could be infrastructure managers, such as AiPo, who would need to invest in the upfront cost for

installation. The revenue will be in term of a fixed subscription fee to be received by the subscriber to the smart navigability service. Further details can be found in the BMC board.

4.3. The Smart Buoy governance framework

The SB, developed in WP2, is designed to survey the navigability of controlled waterways. These buoys can monitor the water levels, localize buoys, count the passing ships, and measure certain environmental parameters such as water depth, current speed, water and air temperature, and wind direction. Additionally, wireless communication with the buoys, ships and sensors will be enabled, as the buoys system is also equipped as a central communication hub. The end users of this technology are barge operators, logistic service providers, waterway managers, and calamity abatement operators. Through the integration of sensors and wireless communication the Intelligent Buoy System will enhance operational efficiency and safety on controlled waterways. The data generated from these buoys will contribute to the planned digital twins of the specific waterway segment and is interoperable with the SCMS platform (ENEA, 2022; Fiedler et al., 2022). As indicated in 2, this system will be implemented in the Polish pilot case.

4.3.1 Governance principles

The governance principles for the SB are linked with the management rules and the division of actor responsibilities in the customer segment and on the management side. These are discussed in 4.3.2.

4.3.2 Organizational structure

The most important actors/stakeholders of the SB are:

- The providers of physical resources, responsible for the supply of SB equipment (buoys, sensors, etc.).
- The Polish Waters (pol. Wody Polskie), which are the owners of the river infrastructure, as they are a governmental organization issuing the permits.
- The Institute of Meteorology and water Economy (IMGW), which is a state-owned company publishing daily reports on water levels of Polish rivers.
- The Certification Body certifying physical resources if required.
- Industrial organizations supporting the promotion of the system.

When looking at the management rules and the division of responsibilities between actors, some other important stakeholders are mentioned. In the customer segments, the infrastructure managers, logistics operators, owners of the means of transport/shipowners, and software companies are mentioned. On the management side, the Polish Waters (pol. Wody Polskie), the CRISTAL project, the University of Gdańsk, L-PIT, and industrial organizations are indicated. These last stakeholders correspond with the ones mentioned before.

4.3.3 Planning and coordination

Process planning in a part of the SB system, and will be implemented by the CRISTAL project, the University of Gdańsk and L-PIT. In addition, coordination mechanisms are part of the SB management system. A community will be built around the solution, sharing and information system for social utility. The solutions

will be co-created with the client in need of the solution. This includes the collaboration with domain software vendors and developers. In 4.3.2., management rules and task/responsibility distribution between actors is discussed. Further details about coordination mechanisms in case of conflicts between these actors are not known yet.

4.3.4 Information collection, sharing, and interoperability

Data generated by the SB will be stored and processed in the data broker. This will be achieved by the mutual review of technologies with a business partner, aiming at the use of existing systems. When needed, a new system will be proposed based on GSM or ISM communication. Afterwards, the flow of information between participants of the IWT process is facilitated and the possibility to propose additional, new services based on the available data is given. These steps can only be achieved if the following protocols, standards and rules are followed:

- Data source: GS1's EPCIS standard in the JSON format
- transfer to the CMS and DT in the JSON EPCIS 2.0 format
- GSM communication for buoy measured data sending to the EPCIS system (in the cloud)
- LPWAN communication in the DASH7 system and/or LoRa: for the device monitoring the bridge clearance and/or beacons on the vessels.

These protocols, standards and rules also ensure data quality, together with the validation of these rules.

Data generated by the SB will eventually be sent to the DT and will then be used by the Smart Monitor for the visualization of this data. This results in the visualization of the river equipped with the SB. Eventually, this visualization should be the base for optimal decision making in the transport sector in Europe. This proves the fact that the SB needs to be interoperable with other systems to be able to make sense of the data generated by it. The following data is generated by the SB and presented by the DT:

- water temperature
- water level (sent also to SCMS - alerts)
- wind speed
- wind direction
- current water direction
- position (coordinates)
- ice cover height (not known yet)
- air temperature
- air pressure
- barge count
- the clearance under the bridge

Additionally, the traffic on the river is measured by counting the amount of passing ships. This is done via alerts based on individual user's threshold sent to the SCMS and DT Alert system subscribers. Therefore, communication with vessels is needed and provided via a module for vessel communication.

4.3.5 Performance monitoring and reporting

To ensure the quality of data and the performance of the SB itself, the data collected from the SB will be analysed in time (DT functionalities) and will be compared to the data collected from other sources such as the IMGW. This will be monitored and reported via de SCMS and DT monitoring and reporting functionalities.

4.3.6 Risk management

The risks and vulnerabilities of the SB will be identified, although the risk management rules and means for avoiding and reacting to threads has yet to be prepared. Therefore, risk management is not yet provided and training and educational resources for actors will maybe be provided in the future.

4.3.7 Regulatory compliance

In terms of regulatory stakeholders, the Polish Waters on behalf of the state government, the IWW infrastructure manager, and the governmental organization issuing the permits are the most important ones. The “Water Law”, the state Inland Waterway Act, is a relevant law for the SB, the General Inland Navigation regulations and the notices to skippers issued on a regular basis by Wody Polskie are relevant regulations for the SB, and the relevant standards regarding the SB are mentioned in 4.3.4. regarding the data collection and sharing. All regulatory compliance will be checked based on permits from the infrastructure manager to install the SB in an environment and conduct the tests.

4.3.8 Stakeholder engagement and communication

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration is ensured via meetings. These meetings were with the infrastructure manager and took place during the development of SB. It is expected to invite Wody Polskie to attend the pilots and SB tests to receive feedback. Communication between stakeholders is provided via the technology provider (L-PIT) and the pilot leader, as they are in constant communication with the infrastructure manager and 3PL operator responsible for the pilot voyages to test the SB during voyages. Communication channels for the stakeholders are planned, but questionnaires for project evaluation and potential further technology development are expected first.

4.3.9 Continuous improvement

As mentioned above, the project evaluation questionnaire for stakeholders is an important feedback document and will have a major impact on how continuous improvement will be further implemented. Tests performed during the pilots will provide the first stakeholder feedback and can affect the potential development of the SB technology (and other technologies). The SB can be easily modified according to future user requirements and can follow the experience and findings received after the test voyages.

4.3.10 Funding and resource management

The business model will be discussed in Deliverable 4.3. However, the supplier of the SB technology is L-PIT now. Prices of the technology are under estimations and cannot be confirmed until tests and

potentially required improvements are implemented. However, there are two business models in consideration:

- Selling the SB direct to the user
- The SB is developed and linked to a platform for data collection. This platform can sell data as the end product.

4.4. The Subsurface Inspection Radar governance framework

The SIR technology will enable the inspection of engineered structures, such as locks and dams, by generating raw data. This data will then be processed by University of Newcastle (UNEW) and will include images allowing the end-users to detect abnormalities caused by defects or damages, and assess the subsurface structure of the inspected asset such as lock walls, concrete dams, ground, etc. In addition, the SIR technology can provide information about the structure of the inspected asset, i.e., lock wall, when the structure or design is unknown (e.g., details on concrete reinforcement). This can be helpful in case of maintenance and predictive maintenance. The SIR technology will collect data periodically and transfer it to the Digital Twin where it will be stored. The end users of this technology will be the infrastructure managers that are responsible for overseeing these structures (ENEA, 2022). The pilot area for this technology is France, and the questionnaire was filled out by the project partners of Euromobilita (EUMO). It is important to note that these radars have already reached a mature and commercial development phase. The implementation of them in the inland waterway infrastructure is innovative at this moment in the project.

4.4.1. Governance principles

The most important aspects and governance principles of the SIR technology are defined as:

- Inspecting the sidewalls of the lock chamber in narrow-gauge and wide gauge locks,
- Inspecting the bottom/bed of the lock chamber,
- Mapping the structure of sidewalls of the lock chamber in narrow-gauge locks,
- Inspecting the earthworks adjacent to sidewalls of the lock chamber, and
- Inspecting dam structures.

4.4.2 Organizational structure

In the questionnaire regarding the SIR technology, questions were asked regarding the most important actors/stakeholders who will use the technologies. For the SIR technology, the IWT owners and maintainers are indicated as most important, though they will have no roles and responsibilities with respect to the SIR technology itself. EUMO and UNEW will offer the technology as a service, while VNF (the French infrastructure manager) provides the existing information about the infrastructure and assets and is responsible for the implementation of the use case. Other interested parties are National Inland Navigation Authorities and potential inspection services suppliers.

4.4.3 Planning and coordination

According to EUMO, process planning regarding the SIR Technology is provided, as the technology is used for scheduled maintenance. It currently involves VNF as the owner of the lock and UNEW and EUMO as the providers of the service and visualisation, as mentioned before. VNF provides the location, and the dates were and when a certain lock needs to be emptied. Additionally, VNF is also responsible for all safety implications, and provides the coordination mechanisms among actors and stakeholders. The latter is in agreement with EUMO and UNEW. Mechanisms in case of conflicts or disagreements between actors and stakeholders are not discussed yet, as the commercial exploitation of the technology and service still needs to happen. When this does happen, contracts will define and dispute these mechanisms. In the current stage of the project, research resolutions are provided by cooperation and discussion between the participating parties.

4.4.4 Information collection, sharing, and interoperability

Data will initially be collected by EUMO, processed by UNEW, and lastly transferred to the Digital Twin. Collected data includes information regarding existing locks, infrastructures and assets, provided by VNF. All data generated by the radars will be shared by electronic transfer, however visual algorithms are needed to be able to comprehend the data. Data from the SIR will therefore not be shared without the visual algorithm developed by UNEW. The shared data will be stored in the Digital Twin and will be visible there for all end-users through the DT Smart Monitor of the related endpoint. Eventually, the data will also be incorporated in the SCMS. The visualisation will incorporate a 2D realization or a rotatable 3D view of the lock, meta information, pictures, and/or videos. The level of details regarding this visualization depends on the available information. As for the protocols regarding the data sharing, storage, and integration, more information will be provided later as these are currently still under development. Overall, data quality is not ensured, although the creators are trying to attempt to provide the best quality data by taking the real-life application scenarios into account. Lastly, the SIR Technology will be interoperable with GPS systems and surface recognition video systems in the future.

4.4.5 Performance monitoring and reporting

According to EUMO, KPIs will be identified during the testing of the technology to ensure the continued efficiency of the system. This will be assessed with a baseline assessment that will benchmark the current performance levels and will identify areas for improvements.

4.4.6 Risk management

Risk and vulnerabilities of the SIR Technology have been identified and therefore, risk management will be provided. The actors that are involved in the development and deployment of the technology (such as an IWT infrastructure owner) are the ones involved and responsible for the risk management. In addition, some current and future challenges were appointed. First, the adaptation and/or development of hardware and software is indicated. Next, the design and implementation of the modular platform integrating all modules and components is a challenge, together with the design and implementation of the operating system and the development of the methods and algorithms for the image processing and visualisation of the generated data.

4.4.7 Regulatory compliance

Many regulatory actors and stakeholders were identified as important in case of the SIR Technology:

- Transportation agencies/infrastructure controllers (e.g., VNF),
- Local government authorities,
- Engineering/construction teams (including 3rd parties) contracted to perform maintenance on large infrastructure assets undergoing SIR survey
- Utility companies if an SIR survey directly concerns a utility with the immediate vicinity of a SIR site survey
- Connected research institutions (e.g., UNEW)
- Residents in the immediate vicinity of SIR survey site (only if the result of SIR surveying will directly lead to significant disruption associated with subsequently informed maintenance efforts)

In terms of laws, five main points have been indicated by EUMO:

- Laws, governing property, rights, and access permissions: an SIR survey should not be conducted on an infrastructure asset without the approval of the authorising/operating body.
- Laws, governing information, security, and privacy: an SIR survey should ensure a reasonable level of data protection to ensure sensitive survey information remains confidential where required.
- Laws governing the mapping of utilities: an SIR survey should comply with local laws, regulating the control of subsurface, surveying and utility tracing within the concern territory.
- Laws, governing research and academic conduct: a SIR surveyor associated with academic/industrial research should not breach guidelines for such research within the associated institution(s).
- Laws/regulations governing site survey when SIR surveys are conducted on large infrastructures and infrastructures under maintenance.

In addition, six standards are indicated as relevant for and are applicable to the SIR Technology:

- EN 15217-2: This European standard, titled “Non-destructive testing - Ground penetrating radar - Part 2: Equipment,” provides specifications for GPR equipment used in non-destructive testing applications. It covers technical requirements for GPR systems and their components.
- CEN/TR 16406: This European Technical Report (CEN/TR) offers recommendations and guidelines for GPR surveys related to utility detection and mapping. It covers equipment specifications, data acquisition, data interpretation, and reporting.
- PAS 128: Although not a formal standard, PAS 128 (Publicly Available Specification 128) is widely used in the United Kingdom for utility mapping and surveying using GPR and other techniques. It provides guidance on data collection, data quality, and data presentation.

- ISO 13124-1: Part of the ISO 13124 series, this standard provides guidelines for the use of GPR in civil engineering and construction applications. It covers topics such as equipment requirements, data acquisition, data processing, and reporting.
- National Standards: In addition to European standards, individual European countries may have their own national standards and guidelines for GPR surveys. These standards can vary from country to country and may address specific regional requirements.
- Industry Best Practices: Various industry associations and organizations in Europe, such as those representing construction, geophysics, and surveying, may offer best practice guidelines and recommendations for GPR survey implementation in specific sectors.

To add to the laws and standards, five regulations have been stated as important. These include:

- Site safety regulations,
- Permits and approvals (if relevant for the site access),
- Traffic management (if not directly handled by the infrastructure controller(s)),
- Data protection and security regulations, and
- Reporting and documentation associated regulations.

All of these regulatory matters need to be tested for compliance. Therefore, some controlling mechanisms have been implied:

- Comprehensive review(s) of regulatory documentation pre-survey agreement,
- Comprehensive SIR survey briefing documentation request from the requesting authority pre-survey agreement,
- Utilising/collaborating with experts in GPR survey technology, when conducting SIR surveys and handling data,
- Comprehensive documentation and reporting of SIR survey timeline (survey request through to completion),
- Regular training and educating of operators and analytics team(s), and
- Consultation with third-party reviewers.

4.4.8 Stakeholder engagement and communication

For the engagement of stakeholders, intermittent meetings in relation to different proposed site investigations are being held. For the communication between actors and stakeholders of the SIR Technology, meetings will be held, and meeting minutes of these meetings will be kept and recorded. In addition, there will be communication channels provided for these actors and stakeholders to share their information, insights, findings, and lessons learned for the technology itself.

4.4.9 Continuous improvement

To further build on the answers from the previous part, continuous improvement will be kept in mind when supplying the SIR Technology. Periodic reviews of the technology are foreseen, and actors and stakeholders will be included in these reviews. Additionally, the feedback received during these reviews will be considered and implemented when the technology gets updated.

4.4.10 Funding and resource management

The last part of the governance framework is the most difficult one. Therefore, we refer to Deliverable 4.3 where business models of all technologies are created and where a cost and benefit analysis has been made.

5. Validation and implementation of the governance framework

The validation of the governance frameworks will in this deliverable only be done internally, and fully validated in the Living Labs (Deliverable 4.4). For the internal validation, this document was sent out to the technology providers together with five questions asking about their opinion about the completeness and correctness of the governance frameworks and possible elements that should be added (now or in the future). These questions can be found in Annex II. In the next parts, the answers will be discussed. Each part discusses one of the three main questions, starting with the governance framework elements, followed by the stakeholders of the technologies and ending with the possible implementation of the framework.

5.1. Governance framework elements

According to the SCMS and DTs technology providers, all necessary elements are included and displayed in their governance frameworks. In both cases, some details on certain issues have not been yet decided upon and should be included in the future. This is mainly because the technologies are not created in real life, but only theoretically as of this moment. Some elements that will need some further discussing and/or should be included in the future are: (final) KPIs for measuring the usefulness and operational performance, well-defined risks and vulnerabilities as well as their mitigation plans, a thorough list of laws, regulations and standards with which both the DTs and SCMS comply, further stakeholder engagement methods and feedback and periodic review systems, and lastly all funding mechanisms. This last one is missing in the case of all technologies, as it is discussed in the business model deliverable (D4.3). This will be added later from the data from the business models.

5.2. Relevant governance framework stakeholders

Here, the technology providers were asked if all necessary stakeholders were included in their governance framework. If any stakeholders are missing, they are added to the governance frameworks above. For the SCMS, the developer and operator of the system, CERTH, and the technological providers providing input for the system (e.g. Fraunhofer for the DTs) were added. The DTs indicated that all stakeholders were included.

5.3. Implementation of the governance framework

Ultimately, we aim at the implementation and use of the created governance frameworks. In case of the SCMS, the governance framework can be implemented and used when all elements are completely defined and addressed. This ensures the viability and the value creation of the technologies. Regarding the DT, the

framework should be feasible. However, as the DTs will be integrated into the SCMS and will not be independent in this project, the framework can only be implemented to a limited extent. If the DTs will work independently (i.e. after the project), the framework should be fully implementable.

5.4. Implementation of the governance framework through the Living Lab

To be able to implement the different governance frameworks in the all pilot scenarios it is necessary to develop a scheme that shows the links between all the stakeholders' groups with the Living Lab users and the links among them. Both Figure 5 and Figure 6 provide an idea of the Living Lab stakeholders' structure.

Figure 5: Stakeholders groups and correlations with Users

Figure 6: Stakeholders groups and correlations among them

Once all the correlations have been highlighted, it becomes easy to identify which stakeholder will be involved in the specific LL event act to present and validate each technology or topic.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable created **six governance frameworks for the six CRISTAL technologies**: the SCMS, DT, AE, FOS, SB, SIR. Each framework was created based on the general GF and the input received from the technology providers via a comprehensive questionnaire. The governance frameworks consist of 10 elements, referring to all important information that must be integrated in the GF. In Table 4 an overview can be found that provides insights into which elements of the generic GF is developed. This overview provides 3 colours which indicates if an element of the GF is developed (green), if an element is partly developed (orange) or not yet developed (red). The full details of what is developed per CRISTAL development can be found in appendix III.

Table 4: Cristal developments in relation to the governance framework

		CRISTAL Developments					
		Digital technologies		Physical technologies			
		SCMS	DT	AE	FOS	SB	SIR
GF elements	Governance principles	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Organizational structure	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Planning and coordination	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Information collection, sharing, and operability	X	X	X	X	X	X

Performance monitoring and reporting	X	X	X	X	X	X
Risk management	X	X	X	X	X	X
Regulatory compliance	X	X	X	X	X	X
Stakeholder engagement and communication	X	X	X	X	X	X
Continuous improvement	X	X	X	X	X	X
Funding and resource management	X	X	X	X	X	X

From Table 4 can be concluded that some parts (or elements) are more complete in the actual GFs than others because of the current phase of development of each technology. This currently results in governance frameworks that can be partially implemented. Eventually, the frameworks will be completed with all necessary elements when in the final stages of the technology development (and the project). Also during the implementation of the living labs (D.4.4) more insights are to be obtained and the GF will be tailored to the specific needs of the different pilots.

Especially for the SMCS still a lot of elements need to be developed for the GF, while for the DT more GF elements are developed. What the two digital CRISTAL technologies have in common is that no KPIs have been developed yet to check if the technology is performing as expected. For the physical technologies most GF elements are developed/identified. Were the GF for the FOS and the SIR are the most far developed. What all technologies have in common is that the “Funding and resource management” element of the GF is not fully developed. The generic and conceptual BM are developed in D.4.3 and will be further tailored in the 3 different living labs (D.4.4).

Another important point is the fact that some technologies will reach another maturity level than others. The AE and SIT technology are the most mature ones and have already reached a mature and commercial stage. However, the implementation of both to inland waterway infrastructures is innovative. As a final step, the governance frameworks were internally validated by the technology providers. This validation has brought the latter discussion regarding the application and implementation of the frameworks and the development phase of the technologies to light. Overall, it can be concluded that the created GFs are a good initial step to further develop them so that the (some) of the CRISTAL technologies can be implemented.

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8. List of tables

Table 1: Authors and contributing partners	7
Table 2 Alignment of D4.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions.....	7
Table 3: Components of a governance framework	9
Table 4: Cristal developments in relation to the governance framework.....	37

9. List of figures

Figure 1: Visualization of the general (theoretical) governance framework.....	10
Figure 2: Technologies and innovations created, implemented, and tested in the CRISTAL project	12
Figure 3: IoT governance roles and responsibilities, source: ENEA	23
Figure 4: IoT data quality conceptual framework	25
Figure 5: Stakeholders groups and correlations with Users	36
Figure 6: Stakeholders groups and correlations among them	37

10. Appendices

Annex I – Questionnaire outline

For the creation of the governance frameworks, as part of WP4 Deliverable 4.2, we need some information regarding the structure and governance of all CRISTAL technologies. Therefore, we would like to ask you some questions with respect to the *TECHNOLOGY*, which you can find below. Could you please provide input for these questions as detailed as possible? If it is not possible to answer a question (or several) at this moment, please indicate this. That way we are able to keep track of the “unknown”.

If you have any additional questions about the questionnaire or about the deliverable, please let us know! Many thanks in advance!

1. Governance principles of the *TECHNOLOGY*
 - a. What are the key (governance) principles that will guide the management and use of the *TECHNOLOGY* and eventually result in good governance (good management) (e.g., security, interoperability, collaboration, data integrity, compliance, etc.)?
2. Organizational structure of the *TECHNOLOGY*
 - a. Can you please revise and/or update the stakeholder frameworks and the stakeholder relationship scheme made in Deliverable 4.1? Please ctrl+click or follow the following path in the shared Teams space: Documents > General > Workspace > WPs > WP04 Governance and Business Models > D.4.1 > Stakeholder Framework. Select the right pilot case and review the three different sheets.
For the French Pilot Case: FRAMEWORK ACTORS - French Case.xlsx
For the Italian Pilot Case: FRAMEWORK ACTORS - Italian Case.xlsx
For the Polish Pilot Case: FRAMEWORK ACTORS - Polish Case.xlsx
 - b. When thinking about the organizational structure of the *TECHNOLOGY*, who will be the most important actors/stakeholders using the SB? 2.3 Which roles and responsibilities will these actors/stakeholders have with regard to the *TECHNOLOGY* (e.g., data quality, security, management of the *TECHNOLOGY*, etc.)?
3. The planning and coordination of the *TECHNOLOGY*
 - a. Will there be any (operational) process planning with regard to the *TECHNOLOGY*? If so, who is involved in the process planning?
 - b. A coordination mechanism is “a social system that coordinates the activities of the people or the organization within the organization”. What will coordination mechanisms among actors/stakeholders of the *TECHNOLOGY* look like, if these mechanisms will be provided?
 - c. Will there be a mechanism in case of conflicts or disagreements between the *TECHNOLOGY* actors/stakeholders?
4. Information collection, sharing, and interoperability of the *TECHNOLOGY*

- a. An important part of the *TECHNOLOGY* is data sharing to the other technologies, how will this happen?
 - b. Will there be any protocols and standards regarding data collection, sharing, storage, and integration? If so, which are these?
 - c. Will all *TECHNOLOGY* actors/stakeholders be able to see (and use) all shared data? If not, which types of information will be shared and which not?
 - d. How is data quality ensured?
 - e. Will the *TECHNOLOGY* be interoperable with other products or systems?
5. Performance monitoring and reporting of the *TECHNOLOGY*
- a. What are the performance indicators of the *TECHNOLOGY*? Are there any that specifically focus on the effectiveness and efficiency of the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - b. How will the performance indicators of the *TECHNOLOGY* be monitored and reported?
6. Risk management of the *TECHNOLOGY*
- a. Will risks and vulnerabilities of the *TECHNOLOGY* be identified?
 - b. Is risk management provided during the creation of the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - c. Which actors/stakeholders are involved in and responsible for the risk management of the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - d. Will training and educational resources provided to actors/stakeholders which are involved in *TECHNOLOGY* activities and/or actors/stakeholders using the *TECHNOLOGY*?
7. Regulatory compliance of the *TECHNOLOGY*
- a. Which regulatory actors/stakeholders are of importance in case of the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - b. Which laws are relevant for and apply to the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - c. Which standards are relevant for and apply to the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - d. Which regulations are relevant for and apply to the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - e. How will compliance with regulatory requirements be checked?
8. Stakeholder engagement and communication within the *TECHNOLOGY*

- a. Will stakeholder engagement and collaboration take place? How (e.g. regular meetings, workshops or feedback mechanisms)?
 - b. Will communication between actors/stakeholders of the *TECHNOLOGY* be possible? If so, will communication mechanisms be provided withing the *TECHNOLOGY*?
 - c. Will communication channels be provided for actors/stakeholders to be able to share their information, insights, findings, and lessons learned from the *TECHNOLOGY*?
9. Continuous improvement of the *TECHNOLOGY*
- a. Will periodic reviews of the *TECHNOLOGY* be foreseen? Will actors/stakeholders be included in these periodic reviews?
 - b. Will the feedback from the periodic reviews be taken into account and eventually be implemented when updating the *TECHNOLOGY*?
10. Funding and resource management of the *TECHNOLOGY*
- a. What is the business model of the *TECHNOLOGY*? Who will be the supplier of the system (at which price)?

Annex II – Validation questions of the governance frameworks

1. Are all elements (regulatory compliance, data sharing, operability, ...) included and correctly displayed in the governance framework?
 - a. If no, which elements should be adjusted?
 - b. Which elements should be added in the future when the development of the technology is at a further stage?
2. Are all relevant stakeholders included in the governance framework?
 - a. If no, who is missing?
3. Do you think that the governance model can be implemented when taking your innovation/technology into account?
 - a. Why yes/no?

Annex III – Detailed overview of the CRISTAL developments in relation to the governance framework

		CRISTAL Developments					
		Digital technologies		Physical technologies			
		SCMS	DT	AE	FOS	SB	SIR
Governance Framework elements	Governance principles	Components to be included such as actors who own/host the SCMS, the revenue scheme, costs and profits	DTs should be able to exchange data in both directions, regardless of the form and size of their respective different functions.	The management of the installation and communication with the data broker are key governance principles	The governance principles of the FOS technology are linked to the FOS specifications and Internet of Things (IoT) solution architecture.	The governance principles for the SB are linked with the management rules and the division of actor responsibilities in the customer segment and on the management side.	The most important aspects and governance principles of the SIR technology are defined
	Organizational structure	Developed in 4.1 includes: Shippers, Logistics service providers or the 3/4/5PL companies, Transport companies, Deepsea and inland ports, Barge operators, Public administration and regulators of IWT, Calamity Abatement Operators, developers	infrastructure managers, transport operators (via the SCMS), and information suppliers (for the SCMS) are the most important actors and stakeholders	The key stakeholders of the AE system are: DT operator, pilot technician, maintenance managers (for port-based infrastructures), calamity abatement operators, barge operators	AIPO & small Medium Enterprise responsible for the production and lease	The infrastructure managers, logistics operators, owners of the means of transport/ship owners, and software companies are mentioned. On the management side, the Polish Waters (pol. Wody Polskie), the CRISTAL project, the University of Gdańsk, L-PIT, and industrial organizations.	The IWT owners and maintainers are indicated as most important, though they will have no roles and responsibilities with respect to the SIR technology itself

<p>Planning and coordination</p>	<p>Coordination mechanisms need to identify the activities provided to coordinate the actors/stake holders of the SCMS. These mechanisms have not been defined yet, although the SCMS will not foresee to foster direct contact through the platform itself.</p>	<p>Process planning will be done as it is required based on D5.1. However, an external coordination mechanism among actors and stakeholders does not exist at the moment now.</p>	<p>As the AE technology is still in the early stages of maturing, no process planning has been provided yet.</p>	<p>Process planning for the FOS technology will follow a typical Life Cycle process, conducted by AiPo.</p>	<p>A community will be built around the solution, sharing and information system for social utility. Further details about coordination mechanisms in case of conflicts between these actors are not known yet.</p>	<p>According to EUMO, process planning regarding the SIR Technology is provided, as the technology is used for scheduled maintenance.</p>
<p>Information collection, sharing, and operability</p>	<p>specific protocols and standards will need to be defined based on the work of CERTH, L-PIT and Fraunhofer regarding the data exchange and sharing.</p>	<p>The individual access rights are decided and distributed by each project pilot.</p>	<p>Data collected via the AE will be shared with the data broker (Fraunhofer). The data will provide a percentage of water lock gate failure, which will be visualized in the DT interface</p>	<p>FOS sensors & ISO/IEC 25000 (data quality), and the ISO 8000 standard (regarding characteristics related to information)</p>	<p>Data generated by the SB will be stored and processed in the data broker. This will be achieved by the mutual review of technologies with a business partner, aiming at the use of existing systems.</p>	<p>Data will initially be collected by EUMO, processed by UNEW, and lastly transferred to the Digital Twin.</p>
<p>Performance monitoring and reporting</p>	<p>The final KPIs that will prove the usefulness of the SCMS have not been decided yet</p>	<p>The final KPIs that will prove the usefulness of the DT have not been decided yet</p>	<p>good acoustic conductance of the sensors on the inspected body</p>	<p>The correct condition of the FOS sensor itself can be checked by the analysis of the spectroscopic signature of its signal</p>	<p>To ensure the quality of data and the performance of the SB itself will be compared to IMGW.</p>	<p>KPIs will be identified during the testing of the technology to ensure the continued efficiency</p>

						of the system.
Risk management	Risks and vulnerabilities identification and mitigation of the SCMS are not included in WP3 activities but can be included in the business model for the SCMS for the different pilots	However, risk management during the creation of the prototypes of the DTs is not provided. The project pilots, technology providers and Fraunhofer IML will further discuss the risk management of the DTs	As AE is a mature technology, meaning it is currently operating, and all relevant risks and vulnerabilities have been identified and addressed.	To avoid these risks, issues and vulnerabilities, risk management will be provided and is managed by the producers (i.e. the SME), the end-users, and the IoT architects.	Risk management is not yet provided and training and educational resources for actors will maybe be provided in the future.	Risk and vulnerabilities of the SIR Technology have been identified and therefore, risk management will be provided
Regulatory compliance	The compliance with regulatory requirements is checked during the development of the SCMS components and functionalities by the developers	as EU Regulation 2018/1725 and the Data Governance Act (DGA), not developed for now	not be applicable for the AE	The most relevant law for the FOS technology is the IEC 61757-1-2, Fibre Optic Sensors – Part 1-2	All regulatory compliance will be checked based on permits from the infrastructure manager to install the SB in an environment and conduct the tests.	Many regulatory actors and stakeholders were identified as important in case of the SIR Technology
Stakeholder engagement and communication	The time plan and method of the stakeholder engagement have not been defined yet	Stakeholder engagement and collaboration will internally take place through meetings	stakeholder engagement and collaboration possibilities are still under process and will be implemented if it is requested	During the creation of the technology, regular project meetings are held between WP2, WP5 and WP7.	Stakeholder engagement and collaboration is ensured via meetings.	For the engagement of stakeholders, intermittent meetings in relation to different proposed site investigations are being held

<p>Continuous improvement</p>	<p>The implementation of periodic reviews in case of the SCMS still have to be decided</p>	<p>Feedback from the project pilots and periodic reviews will be considered during the current development of the DTs</p>	<p>Periodic reviews will be conducted by the pilot's technician. Nothing has been decided on further reviews or feedback moments.</p>	<p>As the FOS technology will not reach the stage of real installation in the Po River, the periodic reviews and stakeholder feedback are only in place during the CRISTAL project time.</p>	<p>Tests performed during the pilots will provide the first stakeholder feedback and can affect the potential development of the SB technology</p>	<p>Periodic reviews of the technology are foreseen, and actors and stakeholders will be included in these reviews</p>
<p>Funding and resource management</p>	<p>This has yet to be decided. Will be created after the first draft of the BM</p>	<p>This has yet to be decided. Will be created after the first draft of the BM</p>	<p>This has yet to be decided. Will be created after the first draft of the BM</p>	<p>This has yet to be decided. Will be created after the first draft of the BM</p>	<p>This has yet to be decided. Will be created after the first draft of the BM</p>	<p>This has yet to be decided. Will be created after the first draft of the BM</p>